

Seasonality of Overnight Stays in European Countries, 1990–2024

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Core results

Seasonality of overnight stays decreased in most European countries in the last decades: From the 38 countries analysed, 27 were clearly able to decrease their seasonality level.

However, the analysis on national level (NUTS-0) is problematic for larger countries and a more detailed look at destination level can reveal large differences within states. At the same time, data from Eurostat are incomplete and not always coherent which makes analysis more difficult.

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Introduction

In this study we assess how seasonality of overnight stays in European countries developed over the last decades.

Scholars in the early 20th century were already well aware of the importance of tourism seasons for demand and supply in tourism (von Schullern zu Schrattenhofen, 1911, p. 486; Warnecke, 1921, pp. 77, 87). Since the early 1970's, seasonality in tourism and hospitality has been systematically studied (Bar-On, 1972, 1973).

Today, some indicator systems for tourism sustainability include seasonality as a factor of the social-economic dimension (De Marchi et al., 2022; Giambona et al., 2024; OECD, 2024; World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), 2024). However, this is not always the case (European Commission, 2016; Miller & Torres-Delgado, 2023). The [EU Tourism Dashboard](#) includes seasonality as a factor in the social-economic dimension.

Assessing seasonality

From the literature we identified five groups of metrics used to assess tourism seasonality. In this study we restrict ourselves to monthly data and a yearly period, although seasonality can also occur in other time units (e.g. hourly, daily, weekly).

Group 1: Peak indicators

In this group, only some data points are used: the peak (maximum) demand, the mean and, sometimes, the minimum value. A special case is the “Top 3 Months” metric. The creators of the EU Tourism Dashboard define this metric: “This indicator is obtained by calculating the

proportion of nights-spent in the three most visited months in relation to the total nights-spent over the year for each destination.”

Group 2: Dispersion indicators

This group is derived from descriptive statistics and reflects the amount of variability in the data. It includes absolute deviation, variance, standard deviation and variation coefficients.

Group 3: Inequality indicators

These indicators were originally developed to reflect socio-economic inequality of income and wealth. For tourism seasonality, the Gini, Theil and Hoover indices are used, with Gini’s coefficient being the most popular.

Group 4: Concentration indicators

These indicators are measuring concentration, with the Herfindahl-Hirschman index being most used, but not in tourism seasonality research.

Group 5: Cyclical indicators

All metrics presented so far are agnostic to the cyclical nature of a calendar, and there are metrics correcting this, with the transport-cost based index by Lo Magno et al. (2017) being concretely applied to tourism seasonality.

Group 6: Seasonal components

Econometric time-series analysis is based upon decomposing time series to allow for better forecasts. The decomposition usually includes a trend, seasonal and residual component. The seasonal component can be used as a measure of the level tourism seasonality (but has never actually been done, to the best of our knowledge).

For this study, we use the “Top-3-Months” indicator and the Corrected Gini coefficient (ranging from 0 to 1). We used the R environment for statistical computing with the DescTools package providing the calculation of the Gini coefficient.

Data

Data were obtained from the Eurostat tourism database (table `tour_occ_nim`). The database holds monthly data on overnight stays (nights spent) at tourist accommodation establishments (hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks) starting in 1990.

The data are both incomplete (gaps in the data) and incoherent (varying statistical bases). We accepted data gaps and did not impute or otherwise replace any data. Incoherences were also accepted and are commented upon in obvious breaks of the time series.

Data were extracted from the database in March 2025 through the publicly available database frontend (ec.europa.eu).

Results

The chart on page 4 illustrates the development of the Top-3-Months share over time per country.

Obviously, there are differences in the *level* of seasonality, ranging from very high levels in Croatia, Montenegro and Bulgaria (with a Top-3-months share of 70% and above) to very moderate seasonality in Liechtenstein, Germany or the Baltic states. These results, however, show limitations of the data analysed: On national level (NUTS-0),

seasonalities of very different destinations within the country are no longer identifiable.

The example of Spain may illustrate this fact: Although on national level only a moderate seasonality can be measured (Spain ranks on position 22 from the 38 countries analysed here), there are regional differences. Observe the seasonality in the Canary islands (“Canarias”) as opposed to the Balearic islands (“Balears”) or the differences in seasonality between Andalusian Costa del Sol and Costa de la Luz in the plot on page 6.

In the EU dataset, for most countries we see a clear **decrease in seasonality** for the years from 1990 to 2019. In 2020 and 2021 we see a sharp rise of seasonality, incurred by the disruptions of the COVID pandemic. After 2021, seasonality usually falls to the pre-pandemic level (and “recovers” more quickly than demand volume).

To quantify the level of change in seasonality, we computed the linear trend per country for the years until 2019. The most prominent long-term decrease can be seen in Iceland (− 0.99 percentage points per year), Luxembourg (− 0.59 percentage points per year) and Denmark (− 0.57 percentage points per year). For countries with shorter time series, Montenegro is showing the most prominent decrease (− 3.05 percentage points per year), followed by Ireland (− 0.59 percentage points per year) and Malta (− 0.57 percentage points per year). 27 of the 38 analysed

countries show a decrease in seasonality (for the years until 2019). Two others, Latvia and Liechtenstein, were quite stable, and nine countries showed an increase of seasonality. However, it seems likely that the reduced number of available datapoints (for Albania and Kosovo) or incoherences in the data (breaks are flagged for Belgium and Denmark in 2015, Netherlands in 2013, Montenegro in 2011 and 2017, and breaks are visible, but not flagged, for Sweden in 2001 and Croatia in 2012) have blurred the picture. If, for example, the trends are computed for Sweden for the periods 1990–2000 and 2001–2019 separately, then a decrease of seasonality can be seen. The same is true for Croatia for the periods 2003–2011 and 2012–2019.

An interesting side result might be that the Top-3-Months share and the Corrected Gini coefficient correlate almost perfectly ($r = .975$). This does not mean that the two indicators are identical, but for practical applications they are mostly interchangeable and, given the many incoherences in the data, lead to comparable results. However, we show the Corrected Gini coefficient in addition to the Top-3-months indicator on page 5.

The detailed results per country and year and the trend coefficients are available under the same DOI as this report.

Yearly seasonality of overnight stays in European countries, 1990–2024 (Top 3 Months)

Data from Eurostat, analysis from NIT using the share of top 3 months per year

Yearly seasonality of overnight stays in European countries, 1990–2024 (Gini)

Data from Eurostat, analysis from NIT using the corrected Gini coefficient

Yearly seasonality of overnight stays in selected Spanish tourist areas, 1999–2024 (Top 3 Months)

Data from INE, analysis from NIT using the share of top 3 months per year

Limitations and outlook

As discussed above, the data have some limitations. Specifically, the analyses on NUTS-0 level might hide more than it shows in some countries. A more detailed analysis on NUTS-2 or NUTS-3 levels or on destination level (as reported for “Reisegebiete” in German tourism statistics or tourist area in the Spanish statistics) would be helpful. The Spanish examples illustrate this.

Even more interesting would be the search for possible causes of the decrease of seasonality on European level. It can be hypothesised that demand grew faster than supply and that capacity limits were reached in the respective high seasons or that demand in year-round destinations (like cities) grew faster than demand in typically seasonal destination (like sun and beach). Another hypotheses could be that suppliers, including DMOs, actively (and successfully) moved the market towards less frequented seasons.

Notes

This document is a working paper of the Institute for Tourism Research in Northern Europe, Kiel. No liability is assumed for the contents.

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